

Administrative System of the Delhi Sultanate

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ABSTRACT

The Sultanate of Delhi was a theocracy. The Sultan was the Caesar and Pope combined in one. It is incorrect to say that there was a secular state then. Islam was the religion of the State, and no other religion was recognized. All the sources of the State were meant for the protection and spread of Islam. Dr. Qureshi thinks that the Sultanate of Delhi was not a theocracy because the rule of the ordained priesthood, an essential feature of theocracy, was absent. This view ignores that canon law was supreme under the Sultanate of Delhi, and civil law was subordinate to it. Indeed, Ulemas in India were not ordained and hereditary. Still, it cannot be denied that they exercised significant influence on the affairs of the State and saw to it that the country's rulers applied the Quranic law. The idea of a Sultan was to convert all the people to Islam and thus turn Dar-ul-Harb, or infidel land, into Dar-ul-Islam or Muslim lands. All kinds of facilities were given to the people to become Muslims. Despite this, the whole of India was not converted to Islam, which was partly due to practical difficulties.

Keywords: Theocracy, The Khalifa, The Sultan, The Nobles, The Ministers, Wazir, Diwan-i-Risalat, Sadr-us-Sudur, Diwan-i-Insha, Barid-i-Mumalik, Wakil-i-dar, Diwan-i-Arz, Naib-ul-Mulk, Sar-i-Jandar, and Jizya

Introduction

The administrative organization of the Delhi Sultanate was a product of many factors. The Sultans of Delhi had before themselves the model of the Government of the Caliph. They had also inherited some of the practices and conventions of the race to which they belonged. They also found a well-established administrative system they could borrow in India. The result was that the Sultans had to assimilate most of the government machinery already existing in the country. Thus, the Government of the Sultans of Delhi has rightly been described as a Turko-Persian System in an Indian Setting.

Theocracy

The political theory of the Islamic State is based on the religious law of Islam, according to which the ultimate authority and the supreme head of the State is God Himself, who rules the worldly kingdom through the Caliph, Sultan, or Padshah. The latter are merely the deputies of God and have no independent position. They are subject to the will of God as expressed in the law. However, subject to those limitations, they can do whatever they like. All Muslim rulers indeed had the right to interpret the law, but they had to depend upon the leading theologians for its interpretation. Thus, the Muslim State was undoubtedly a theocracy. The Sultans of Delhi never discarded this basis of the Muslim State; hence, the Delhi Sultanate continued to be a theocracy. The fact that the law of Islam, as propounded by the four schools of jurisprudence, did not suffice to cover all the new situations and problems arising in the Muslim States did not affect the essential character of the State. The Sultans admitted that the Muslim law could not guide them in every sphere. Consequently, they had to depart from the law in some instances, but that was only in matters of detail and did not affect the basic concept that the Islamic State was an organized agency founded by God Himself to propagate Islam through the instrumentality of the earthly rulers.

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rulers applied the Quranic law. The idea of a Sultan was to convert all the people to Islam and thus turn Dar-ul-Harb, or infidel land, into Dar-ul-Islam or Muslim lands. All kinds of facilities were given to the people to become Muslims. Despite this, the whole of India was not converted to Islam, which was partly due to practical difficulties.

Dr. Habibullah states, "The chronicles tend to give us an impression that the Sultanate was a truly Islamic state, constantly striving to make its policy conformable to the Shariah. That it was scarcely so in actual practice will have been gathered from the last few chapters. We have noticed the un-Islamic character of the kingship; Barani admits that '**duniyadari**,' of which kingship is the highest perfection, is opposed to '**dindari**.' After tracing the process by which the pagan institution of monarchy had crept into Islam, he concludes that sovereignty is never possible without practicing non-Islamic customs. Conscientious ecclesiastics might delude themselves that the Sultan existed to protect the faith and uphold the **Shariah**. Still, it requires little stressing that the decisive factor in his actions was the law of force and expediency. In summing up his account of the origin and nature of kingship, Barani remarks that the meaning of kingship is still power, whether obtained by lawful means or force; even the older pagan law of dynastic legitimacy finds no place in the present kingship. In ordinary practice, the shariah was no more respected than any other law. Barani admits that capital punishment of Muslims, contrary to the Sacred Law, was necessary for the necessities of a better Government.

Similarly, the law of inheritance, the strict distinction between halal and haram, and many other well-known injunctions were violated; the ecclesiastics protested but were constrained to find excuses. The famous prohibition of the shariah regarding the taking and giving of interest on monetary transactions was openly disregarded: Amir Khusrau mentions the rate of interest at one vital per month for the principal sum of the **tanka**, which, when agreed upon by the parties on a written bond, had a legal sanction and was enforced by the **qazi**. Of the four conditions which Barani advises the king to bear in mind when issuing decrees (zabitah), one is that if any of the proposed ordinances are found contrary to the shariah, it need not be withdrawn but, as an evil necessity is to be retained not longer than is necessary.

"Even the majority of the **ulema**, the guardians of the sacred law, was utterly materialistic in outlook and opportunist in conduct. They entered into an unholy alliance with the secular authorities and, by distorting the rules of the **shariah**, found sanction for Sultan's pagan practices. Even traditions from the Prophet were concocted to give the king's despotism a moral backing. They held out that the Sultan's office was only slightly inferior to that of the Prophet

and his sanctity almost equal to that of God. To suit the Sultan's convenience, his religious duties were confined to leading the prayers, making endowments for the alema and religious establishments, and dispensing justice. At the same time, the most flagrant breaches of the Shariah rules, like drinking, non-observance of the fast, etc., were condoned. The ulema even authorized him to appropriate the people's wealth whenever he desired."

Administrative Organisation

The foreign elements in the Sultanate consisted of the Central Ministry, their military system, and modifications of the taxation policy as well as tax structure of the country to some extent by the enhancement of the rate of land revenue and by the addition of certain new taxes such as lit pilgrimage tax, heavier duties on Hindus and other non-Muslims than on the Muslim merchants. All non-Muslims were deprived of citizenship status and were accepted merely as Zimmis. They had to obtain their security of life and property by payment of a money consideration and their rights to perform their religious duties by payment of religious taxes. Moreover, all higher positions carrying immense powers and emoluments were reserved for Muslims only. There was no opening for the Hindus. While the outer framework of the administrative machinery, particularly in the lower rungs of the hierarchy, would seem to have been built on the earlier pattern, the spirit and policy of the Turkish Government were transformed. There is no merit or substance in the contention of some writers that the Delhi Sultanate was a democracy. This claim is refuted because the Hindus, who comprised most of the population, had no say in the country's administration.

The Khalifa

The Caliph, or the Khalifa, was the king of all the Muslims in all parts of the world. Still, with the spread of Islam in various parts of the world, it became practically impossible to enforce the authority of the Khalifa everywhere. However, the fiction of the unity of the Khalifa was maintained. This was continued even though the last Khalifa was put to death by Hustan Khan, the Mongol leader. What was done was that the Sultans of Delhi described themselves as the Deputy or Assistant of the Khalifa. They received investiture from the Khalifa, inscribed his name on their coins, and got the Khutba read in the name of the Khalifa. Ala-ud-Din Khalji refused to recognize the authority of the Khalifa, and Qutb-ud-Din Mubarak himself took up the title of the Caliph. Excepting these two rulers, the other Sultans of Delhi recognized the nominal charge of the Khalifa. However, no Sultan of Delhi bothered to obey the Khalifa; No Sultan believed that he got his authority from the Khalifa. Sultans of Delhi considered it more profitable

to maintain their contacts with the outside Muslim world, and no wonder they recognized the nominal charge of the Khalifa.

The Sultan

The Sultan was the head of the Delhi Sultanate. He was the source of all power and authority. He was the sovereign head and commander of the army. His will was law. It was the duty of everyone to obey his command. Generally, the Sultans of Delhi maintained the form of an election. The nobles, the landlords, and the most influential Ulema at the capital agreed upon a candidate and declared him the Sultan. Afterward, a formal oath of allegiance was taken by them and later on by the people. It cannot be denied that the election procedure was merely a fiction. The candidate had already decided the issue by conquest in battle and by overwhelming force. Of course, it had the advantage of being legal and conforming to the wishes of the jurists and the people. An attempt was made to choose from the ruling family, but the hereditary principle was not always followed. Although Jalal-ud-Din Khalji had already seated himself on the throne, the outward election form was maintained. Many people did not take the oath of allegiance to the Khaljis for some time, but they did so after some time.

Most jurists believed the Sultan could be deposed if he failed to maintain his trust; Injustice was considered a sufficient cause for dethronement. All writers agree that a man suffering from a mental or physical infirmity could not continue to be sovereign; great importance was attached to the loss of power of judgment and eyesight. The very fact that a large be sacrosanct. There were indeed intrigues and rebellions even against competent rulers, but several Delhi Sultans who were removed from the throne show that they were not considered to be those with little chance of success.

The Sultan was required to be capable of dealing with the State's problems. He was to be in full possession of physical and mental faculties. Ordinarily, the ruler was expected to be a male, and no wonder the election of Sultana Razia created a lot of trouble.

The absence of a hereditary principle of succession indeed had its defects but enabled many brilliant men to be the rulers of Delhi. It was not easy to occupy the throne of Delhi, and no wonder fools and pleasure-seekers could not afford to remain long on the throne. The Delhi Sultanate required all the care and work a man could give. The rough and ready method of selecting the Sultan worked well, and the right man was found at the right time.

The Sultan was recognized as the supreme interpreter of the law but could not go against the recognized interpretation. He couldn't disregard Ijma or preponderant concurrence of opinion on any point. Where the jurists disagreed, the Sultan could make his own decision, but while doing so, he was to get the advice of the learned jurists. The Sultan was expected not to contradict the **Sharia** while making laws. The sovereignty of law was not merely a legal fiction. The Sultans of Delhi showed remarkable respect for the **Sharia** in their public dealings. There were indeed certain violations, but in many cases, even the mighty Sultans humbled themselves before the majesty of the law.

The Sultan enjoyed great prestige. They were considered to be the heart of the system. Their existence was the primary necessity of social life. Without a ruler, all order would vanish, and the human race's existence could be endangered. It was his sword that cleansed the world of anarchy and evil. A just Sultan could expect to find a place under the banner of the Prophet on the day of reckoning. It was the duty of the Sultan to give complete protection to the people to develop themselves.

The Sultan was expected to protect Islam. He was to settle disputes among his subjects. He was required to defend the territories of Islam and keep the highways and roads safe for travelers. He was to maintain and enforce the criminal code. He was to strengthen the frontiers of Muslim territory against possible aggression. He was to wage a holy war against those hostile to Islam. He was to collect rates and taxes. He was to apportion the shares of those who deserved an allowance from the public treasury. He was to appoint officers to help him in his general and legal duties. He was required to keep in touch with public affairs and the condition of the people by personal contact. "The Sultan controls affairs, maintains right and enforces the criminal code; he is the Pole Star around which revolve the affairs of the world and the Faith; he is the protection of God in his realm; his shadow extends its canopy over his servants, for he forbids the forbidden, helps the oppressed, uproots the oppressor and gives security to the timid."

It is not proper to contend that the Sultan was absolutely a despot and that there was a limitation on his power. However, in actual practice, absolute authority exists only in the despot's dream. All political power is limited and depends on the cooperation of solid elements in the State.

The Nobles

The nobles put a very effective check on the king's power. No Sultan could afford to offend the powerful nobles without endangering his position. Some of these nobles were the

heads of clans and consequently had a permanent following. It took work to impose the royal will on them. They considered themselves to be the equals of the Sultan and capable of founding royal dynasties themselves. Their relationship with the Sultan varied according to the character and capability of the Sultan. The only ideal that held the nobles together was the service of Islam. It was realized that a faith without a state and a state without a religion without guidance were futile. These feelings kept the nobles together, and they obeyed the Sultan as long as they felt he was performing his duties. The nobles did not hesitate to revolt against him if he was incapable. It must be remembered that the nobles often did what was advantageous to them.

The Ministers

There is an Arab adage that "The bravest of men require arms, and the wisest of kings need ministers," the same was true of the Delhi Sultans. During the rule of the so-called Slave dynasty, there were four ministers, viz, the Wazir, the Ariz-i-Mamalik, the Dewan-i-Insha, and the Diwan-i-Rasalat. Sometimes, the Naib or Naib-i-Mamalik was also appointed. He exercised great authority mainly when the Sultan was weak. Ordinarily, he was inferior to Wazir. Later, the Sadr-us-Sudur and Diwan-i-Qaza's offices were raised to the ministers' status. Thus, there were six ministers under the Delhi Sultanate. The Comptroller of the Royal household was not technically a minister but exercised more extraordinary powers than a minister did.

The Delhi Sultans were surrounded by the wisest and most experienced men in the realm. They had beautiful opportunities to seek advice and counsel and keep in touch with public opinion. The ministers were just the servants of the Sultan and responsible to him alone. However, this does not mean that a minister had no absolute authority. The position and powers of a minister were well-defined by law and sanctified by tradition.

Wazir

The chief minister was called the **Wazir**, and great importance was attached to this post. The Wazir stood mid-way between the sovereign and his subjects. He was considered to be a partaker in sovereignty. It was recognized that no empire could be stable or prosperous without a Wazir: "Sovereignty and dominion could not be the pinnacle of their height without the help and cooperation of a Wazir, whose wise deliberations would result in promoting the welfare of the country and the prosperity of the people."

Diwan-i-Risalat

There is a difference of opinion among scholars regarding the functions of Diwan-i-Risala. The view of Dr. Qureshi is that he dealt with religious matters and was also in charge of the grant of stipends to scholars and pious men. However, the idea of Dr. Habibullah is that he was minister for foreign affairs and was in charge of diplomatic correspondence. Ambassadors and envoys were sent to and received from foreign rulers. It is pointed out that the view of Dr. Habib Ullah is preferable. One officer was already in charge of religious affairs, endowments, and charity, and he was known as Sadr-us-Sudur.

Sadr-us-Sudur

Very often, the offices of Sadr-us-Sudur and Diwan-i-Qaza were held by one person. The Sadr-us-Sudur was required to enforce Islamic rules and regulations. He needed to see that the Muslims observed those rules and limitations daily. He had in his charge a lot of money to give to Muslim divines, scholars, and men of piety. The head of the Diwan-i-Qaza was the Qazi-i-Mumalik, also known as Qazi-i-Quzat.

Diwan-i-Insha

The Diwan-i-Insha dealt with royal correspondence. It has rightly been called "the treasury of secrets." That is because Dabir-i-Khas, who presided over this department, was also the confidential clerk of the State. The Dabir-i-Khas were assisted by several Dabirs who had established their reputation as masters of style. All correspondence between the sovereign and the rulers of other states or his tributaries and officials passed through this department. Every order from the Sultan was first drafted in this department and then taken to him for sanction, after which it was copied, registered, and despatched.

Barid-i-Mumalik

The Barid-i-Mumalik was the head of the state news agency. His duty was to keep himself informed of everything happening in various parts of the empire. There was a local Barid at the headquarters of every administrative sub-division, and it was his duty to send regular newsletters to the Central Office. It is only men of honesty who were appointed to this post. If a Barid did not report a misdeed or some gross injustice committed by a well-placed official, he sometimes had to pay for his mistake with his life. There was nothing that was outside the sphere of the Barid. He was the confidential agent of the Central Government to report on every aspect of public administration. He was required to register the Government officials, the financial

position, the State of agriculture, purity of coinage, etc. He was required to send his impressions regarding the review of troops. He attended all critical functions. He kept his informers everywhere and did not allow anything to escape. The Barid was paid well so that he may be above temptation.

Wakil-i-dar

The Wakil-i-dar was the chief dignitary of the royal household. He controlled the entire family and supervised the payment of allowances and salaries to the personal staff of the Sultan. The royal kitchen, stables, and even the children of the Sultan were under his control. All royal orders relating to the household were communicated through him. He reported all affairs requiring royal sanction. Everybody was required to approach the Sultan through him; consequently, he exercised significant influence and was considered the deputy of the Sultan in many respects. As he was constantly dealing with men of importance, he was required to be exceedingly tactful. Even his staff was selected very carefully. He had to keep the Sultan well-informed about the affairs of the State, mainly because most of the crucial personages with whom he dealt had direct access to the Sultan.

Diwan-i-Arz

The Ariz-i-Mumalik was the head of the ministry of war called Diwan-i-Arz. He was responsible for maintaining the army in a state of efficiency. He acted as the chief recruiting officer and fixed the salary of each recruit. He inspected the troops at least once a year and examined the condition of the equipment of every trooper. The promotion of every soldier depended upon him. He kept Master rolls and revised the salaries at each annual review. His office was responsible for the recommendation of assignments to soldiers and the payment of the troops. The Ariz was in charge of all preparations whenever a campaign was undertaken. Although the general was nominated by the Sultan, the choice of the troops was generally to him. In all crucial wars, he accompanied the army. He looked after supply and transport. After a victory, he supervised the booty collection divided in the presence of the Commander-in-chief. The Diwan-i-Arz was rightly called the "source of the livelihood of the fighters for the Faith."

Naib-ul-Mulk

Under the Delhi Sultanate, a noble was generally selected as Naib-ul-Mulk or Lord Lieutenant of the realm. The actual authority varied with the character of the Sultan. Sometimes, it was merely an empty title, but the Naib-ul-Mulk was practically the absolute authority at other

times. He was the head of the military organization and was entrusted with the Government of the centrally administered areas. A noble was selected to act as Naib-i-Ghaibat during the absence of the Sultan. He was the representative of the Sultan at the capital and dealt with all emergent and routine business.

Sar-i-Jandar

The Sar-i-Jandar was attached to the Court. He commanded the king's bodyguard called Jandars. He was a salaried officer and a high noble. There appeared to be more than one Sar-i-Jandar at a time, possibly in command of different groups. His primary duty was to guard the person of the king. The Jandar formed an integral part of his entourage. A passage in the Tabage-Nasiri suggests that the Sar-i-Jandar was also entrusted with the custody, punishment, and execution of the prisoners of war and convicted criminals.

The other household dignitaries were Amir-i-Akhur (Master of Horse) with his Naib and the Shahnah-i-Pilan (Superintendent of Elephants). The Amir-i-Shikar was in charge of the hunting establishment of the king. He had several subordinates to look after different hunting animals and birds.

The Amir-i-Hajib, his Deputy, the Wazir, Ariz, the Vakil-i-dar, and the Kotwal of Delhi formed a kind of Advisory Council for the Sultan. However, there was no hard and fast rule as to its constitutional functions, and much depended upon the whim of the Sultan. Non-officials were also customarily consulted. The officials and the non-officials were together known as Arkan-i-Daulat. Bhugra Khan was specially instructed to follow the advice of these advisers. Kaiqubad was urged to refer all problems of Government to his Cabinet of four Ministers, composed of the Wazir, Ariz, and the Heads of the Diwan-i-Insha and Diwan-i-Risalat.

Finance

The fiscal policy of the Sultanate period was based on the theory of finance of the Hanafi School of Sunni jurists. The Muslim State had two revenue sources: religious and secular. The religious taxes could be demanded only from the Muslims, which were grouped under Zakat's name. It was an act of piety to pay Zakat. The Zakat was payable in gold or silver, herds, and merchandise. The Zakat was 1/40th of the property when assessed on value or weight. Zakat could be levied only on that property in the owner's possession for at least one year. There is a mention of a separate treasury for Zakat.

The secular taxes were Khuraj and Jizya, the tax on non-Muslim traders and imposts on spoils of war, on mines and treasure-trove. Kharaj was the tax on land held by non-Muslims. According to Islamic law, its rate varied from 1/10th to one-half.

Jizya

Jizya was a poll tax charged only to the non-Muslims. There is a difference of opinion among scholars regarding the nature of this tax. One view is that it was a religious tax levied on the non-muslims "in return for which they received the protection of life and property and exemption from military service, as non-Muslims were not entitled," according to orthodox jurists, to live in a Muslim country. The view of Dr. Qureshi is that Jizya was levied from the non-Muslims as the cash equivalent "of the assistance which they would be liable to give if they had not persisted in their unbelief, because living as they do in the Muslim state, they must be ready to defend it." Military service was compulsory for all Muslims, and the Sultan could call upon any Muslim to defend the State. This religious duty did not affect the non-Muslims. This shows that Jizya was not a payment for the privilege of living in a Muslim state.

Critics point out that whatever might have been the original intention with which Jizya was levied in Islamic lands outside India, there is no doubt that by the time the Arabs conquered Sind, Jizya had acquired a religious importance. Jizya was assessed on the non-Muslims as the State gave them "protection of life and property and exemption from military service." The Sultans considered it a religious duty to realize the Jizya with all the rigor they could command. It is pointed out that those who hold Jizya to be a secular tax ignore the fact that it was levied in place of the protection of the life and property of the Zimmis and put emphasis merely on exemption from military service. It is well known that even the vassal Hindu Rajas who rendered military service were not exempted from the payment of Jizya. Jizya was not levied on women, children, monks, beggars, blind people, and people with disabilities. It was not imposed even on the Brahmanas. Only during the reign of Firuz Shah was Jizya assessed on the Brahmanas. There was a lot of trouble, and ultimately, the wealthy Hindus of Delhi undertook to pay for the Brahmanas. On a subsequent representation, the Sultan reduced the tax on the richer Brahmanas to 10 Tankas of 30 Jitals each. The entire Hindu population was divided into three grades for Jizya. The first grade paid at the rate of 48 Dirhams, the second 24 Dirhams and the third 12 Dirhams.

The Zakat on imports was a fortieth of the value of the merchandise. It was 50% on horses: These charges were double for non-Muslim traders. Sikandar Lodi abolished the Zakat

on grain and was not renewed by any subsequent Sultan. The spoils of war were known as Ghanimah. Legally, out of all the booty collected, one-fifth would be kept for the State, and the rest would be distributed among the soldiers. However, it was lawful for the Sultan or Commander-in-Chief to select an animal, a sword, or an article that particularly pleased him. The share of the State was known as **Khams**. Against Islamic law, a practice grew that only a fifth was distributed amongst the soldiers, and the State kept four-fifths. The State was entitled to a fifth of all minerals, provided those were solid and could be melted. A fifth of the treasure trove was to be given to the State, and the finder kept the rest. However, if the land did not belong to the finder, the landowner was entitled to four-fifths of the treasure, and the rest would go to the State. The property of the Muslims dying intestate and without heirs belonged entirely to the State. However, the property of a Hindu dying in similar circumstances was handed over to his community.

Land Revenue

The primary source of income of the Sultan was the land revenue. There were four kinds of land viz, Khalisa territory, land divided into Iqtas and held by Muqtis either for several years or for a lifetime, principalities of the Hindu chiefs who had come to terms with the Sultan, and the land given away to Muslim scholars, and saints in a gift. The Khalisa land was directly administered by the Central Government. However, the State dealt only with the local revenue officers and not the individual peasants. An Amil or revenue clerk in each sub-division collected revenue from the peasants. The shares of the State were based on a summary assessment. The assessment and collection of income in the lata was in the hands of the Muqti, who deducted his share and paid the surplus to the Central Government. The Sultan appointed an officer called Khwaja in each Iqta to supervise the revenue collection and also to check the Mut. There was a possibility of cooperation between the Muqti and the Khwaja. The Wakf land, or inam land, was free from revenue assessment.

Conclusion

We may conclude by saying that, on the whole, the administration of the Delhi Sultans was a sort of military rule maintained by fear of force. It was not based on the consent of the people. Ordinarily, the Government was worried only about collecting money from the people. It did not consider its responsibility for their welfare. The non-Muslims, who comprised most of the population, were ignored entirely. The result was that the position of the Sultans could have been more stable, and we have references to frequent revolts against the authority of Sultans.

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